

Learning Perceptual Hash Similarity for Image Copy Detection

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Abstract—Image copy detection is commonly addressed using either local descriptors or deep learning models, which can be computationally expensive and rely on high-dimensional features. In contrast, this work explores copy detection using compact perceptual hash representations and learned similarity functions defined directly on hash codes. We evaluate classical hash distances under realistic transformations using the PIHD dataset and assess generalization on a modified MS COCO dataset (mCOCO). We propose SiPHaD, a Siamese-based model that learns similarity in hash space, improving retrieval performance while maintaining efficiency. Results demonstrate that lightweight hash-based approaches, when combined with learned similarity, provide a strong alternative to feature-heavy pipelines.

Index Terms—Copy Detection, Perceptual Hashing, Siamese Network

I. INTRODUCTION

Image copy detection aims to identify near-duplicate images under geometric, photometric, or content-preserving transformations. It is critical in applications such as digital forensics [1], counter-terrorism [2] and detection of harmful or illegal visual content [3]. In practice, images are rarely stored in their original form and are often modified through operations such as blurring, overlays, resizing, cropping, color shifts, distortions, rotation, and mirroring (Fig. 1), making reliable detection challenging.

Copy detection is a fundamental problem in multimedia retrieval, with applications in copyright enforcement, plagiarism detection, and large-scale visual search [4, 5, 6, 7]. Existing approaches are broadly divided into local feature-based and global representation-based methods. Local descriptors offer strong robustness to transformations but require significant storage and computation. Global representations are more compact but typically depend on supervised or domain-specific training data, limiting their applicability. These trade-offs motivate lightweight and scalable alternatives.

Perceptual hashing provides a compact representation by encoding each image into a binary code that captures its visual content [8]. Classical methods, including A-Hash, D-Hash, P-Hash, and W-Hash, are efficient and robust to minor varia-

Fig. 1: Overview of common image modifications.

tions, but their discriminative power degrades under strong transformations, occlusions, or structural changes [9]. Despite these limitations, they remain attractive in scenarios with strict constraints on storage, computation, or training data.

To address the limitations of fixed hash distances, we investigate learned similarity functions directly in the hash space. We propose Siamese Perceptual Hashing Distance (SiPHaD¹), a framework that combines perceptual hashes with a Siamese network to learn robust similarity between hash codes. The model operates solely on binary hashes and requires only labeled hash pairs, without access to original images. In addition, we evaluate multiple similarity measures—bitwise (Hamming, Cosine, Jaccard), spatial-aware (Chamfer, Convolution, Hatched), and sequential (N-Gram)—to analyze their effectiveness and interaction with learned similarity.

Existing datasets for copy detection are often limited in size, realism, or reproducibility [8]. The PIHD dataset [10] includes only single modifications and lacks detailed generation protocols. To address these limitations, we introduce mCOCO, a dataset derived from MS COCO that includes both single and combined transformations for more realistic evaluation.

The main contributions of this work are:

- 1) A Siamese-based model (SiPHaD) that learns robust similarity between perceptual hashes.

¹<https://github.com/jmstf94/Perceptual-Hashing-Image-Retrieval.git>

TABLE I: Perceptual hashing methods. ψ, χ denote Haar wavelets, δ the Kronecker delta. L_0 and L select low-frequency components.

Method	Abbreviation	Resize	Weights	Binarization
Average	A-Hash	$n \times n$	$\delta_{lw} \delta_{sh}$	$T_{ls} > \text{mean}(T)$
Difference	D-Hash	$(n+1) \times n$	$\delta_{lw} \delta_{sh}$	$T_{(l+1)s} > T_{ls}$
Perceptual	P-Hash	$4n \times 4n$	$\cos \frac{\pi(2w+1)l}{8n} \cos \frac{\pi(2h+1)s}{8n}$	$T_{ls}^{(n)} > \text{mean}(T^{(n)})$
Wavelet	W-Hash	$2n \times 2n$	$(L \circ \chi \circ \psi^{-1} \circ L_0 \circ \psi)(w, h, s, l)$	$T_{ls} > \text{median}(T)$

- 2) A new dataset (mCOCO) for evaluating image retrieval under realistic transformations.
- 3) A comprehensive comparison of perceptual hashing methods and similarity metrics.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section II reviews prior work. Section III presents the proposed framework. Section IV describes the datasets and experimental setup. Section V reports the results, and Section VI concludes the paper.

II. RELATED WORK

This section reviews prior work on image retrieval and authentication, including local features (Section II-A), global and deep methods (Section II-B), perceptual hashing (Section II-C), and datasets (Section II-D).

A. Local Feature-Based Methods

Local feature-based approaches are widely used due to their robustness to geometric transformations, viewpoint changes, occlusion, and illumination variations [4, 5, 6]. Classical methods rely on hand-crafted descriptors such as SIFT, SURF, and ORB to extract and match keypoints across images [11]. Aggregation schemes, including bag-of-visual-words and inverted indexing, enable large-scale retrieval.

To improve scalability, prior work has explored memory-efficient representations and faster similarity computation. Methods such as AMES [12] decouple query and database representations, while indexing structures such as NV-tree [13] support efficient retrieval at scale. Despite their robustness, these approaches require storing many descriptors per image, resulting in high memory and computational cost.

B. Global Feature Representations and Deep Learning

Global representations encode each image as a single high-dimensional vector, providing a compact alternative. Early approaches used hand-crafted features, while recent methods employ deep neural networks to learn discriminative embeddings [14, 15]. These representations enable efficient nearest-neighbor search and reduce storage requirements.

However, their effectiveness often depends on supervised or domain-specific training data. In practice, such data may be limited or unavailable, and models may suffer from domain shift. Deep hashing methods further compress embeddings into binary codes [16, 17, 18, 19, 20], but typically require large labeled datasets and significant computational resources.

C. Perceptual Hashing Techniques

Perceptual hashing encodes images into compact binary representations for efficient similarity computation [8, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26, 27]. Classical methods include A-Hash, D-Hash, P-Hash, and W-Hash, which are commonly compared using Hamming distance [28]. Table I summarizes these classical methods, highlighting differences in preprocessing scale, weighting design, and binarization strategy (more info in Section III-A).

Image modifications are typically grouped into: (1) photometric: changes in pixel values (e.g., blur, noise, color shifts and (2) spatial: geometric transformations (e.g., cropping, resizing, rotation).

Classical perceptual hashes are efficient and interpretable, making them suitable for constrained settings. They evolved from local descriptors such as FDoG and SIFT [29], to saliency-based [30], geometric [31], and multi-scale methods [32]. However, their robustness remains limited under strong transformations, motivating more advanced approaches.

D. Datasets for Evaluation

Datasets for copy detection typically include original images, content-preserving variants, and visually distinct images. Early datasets often applied simple modifications (e.g., cropping, rotation, noise) to images from COCO [33], ImageNet [34], or CASIA [35], making tasks easier and less realistic. The PIHD dataset [10], created alongside this work, includes only single modifications per image. To capture more complex transformations, we developed mCOCO, featuring both uni- and multimodal modifications.

III. METHODOLOGY

This section presents our approach to robust image copy detection, which aims to identify whether a query image is a copy or near-duplicate of a database image under transformations such as scaling, rotation, or color changes. Each image is represented by a perceptual hash, and a similarity function $f(h_i, h_j) \in [0, 1]$ measures the similarity between the d -dimensional hashes h_i and h_j of images I_i and I_j , where higher values indicate greater similarity. For retrieval, query hashes are compared against database hashes and ranked accordingly. This framework supports both classical similarity metrics and our learned SiPHaD model, detailed in Section III-C, where we show its robustness to crops, scaling, and other distortions. We first introduce perceptual hashing (Section III-A), followed by baseline similarity metrics (Section III-B), and then present the SiPHaD model.

Fig. 2: Overview of the SiPHaD Siamese architecture. A positive (similar) and a negative (dissimilar) image pair are processed using identical branches with shared weights. Images are converted to perceptual hashes, embedded into a common space, and compared using a distance function that is mapped to a similarity score. The model is trained using contrastive loss.

TABLE II: Classical similarity measures for perceptual hashes.

Category	Method	Definition / Description
Bitwise	Hamming	$1 - \frac{1}{d} \sum_i h_{1,i} - h_{2,i} $
Bitwise	Cosine	$\frac{\sum_i h_{1,i} h_{2,i}}{\ h_1\ \ h_2\ }$
Bitwise	Jaccard	$\frac{ h_1 \cap h_2 }{ h_1 \cup h_2 }$
Spatial	Chamfer	Distance between active bit locations
Spatial	Convolution	Similarity via 2D hash convolution
Spatial	Hatched	Row/column alignment via Hamming match
Sequential	N-gram Cosine	Cosine similarity of n -gram vectors

A. Perceptual Hashing

Perceptual hashes compactly represent an image while remaining partially invariant to transformations such as scaling, rotation, or color changes. Each image uses one of four standard hashes—A-Hash, D-Hash, P-Hash, or W-Hash—avoiding sub-region methods for simplicity and efficiency.

For all methods, the pipeline is identical: the RGB image is first converted to grayscale, $[I_{wh} = 0.299 I_{whR} + 0.587 I_{whG} + 0.114 I_{whB}]$, then resized using Lanczos resampling [36], $[I_{wh} = \sum_i \sum_j L(w, i) L(h, j) I_{ij}]$ where L denotes the Lanczos kernel. Hash-specific weights produce features, $T_{ls} = \sum_{w,h} w_{lsw} I_{wh}$, which are binarized and flattened into a 1D hash, $H = \text{flatten}(B(T_{ls}))$. This pipeline is shared by all methods, with differences in resize dimensions, weights, and comparison functions listed in Table I, where w and h are width and height indices, and n is the base size. Additionally, it shows the binarization B_{ls} ; the final 1D hash is $H = \text{flatten}(B_{ls})$.

B. Classical Similarity Measures

We summarize common similarity measures for perceptual hashes $h_i \in \{0, 1\}^d$, grouped into bitwise, spatial, and sequential categories. Table II lists representative methods with their representations and assumptions. Bitwise measures ignore spatial structure, spatial methods assume geometric consistency, and sequential approaches capture local patterns.

However, none of these measures fully model perceptual similarity, motivating our learned approach in Section III-C.

C. SiPHaD Model

SiPHaD is a learned similarity framework designed to compare perceptual hashes directly for image copy detection. Given two images I_i and I_j , each image is first converted into a perceptual hash using one of the methods described in Section II-C, yielding binary representations $h_i, h_j \in \{0, 1\}^d$ (or their 2D forms $B_{ls}^{(i)}, B_{ls}^{(j)}$).

As illustrated in Fig. 2, SiPHaD follows a Siamese design in which pairs of images are processed through identical branches with shared parameters. Positive (similar) and negative (dissimilar) pairs are mapped into a common embedding space, where distances are computed to capture perceptual similarity.

Formally, let a perceptual hash be represented as $h = \text{flatten}(B_{ls}) \in \{0, 1\}^d$. The Siamese network defines a shared embedding function $\phi_\theta : \{0, 1\}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^m$, parameterized by θ . For a given hash pair (h_i, h_j) , the embeddings are $z_i = \phi_\theta(h_i)$, $z_j = \phi_\theta(h_j)$, and a distance is computed in the embedding space: $d_\theta(h_i, h_j) = \mathcal{D}(z_i, z_j)$. The similarity function is then defined as

$$f_\theta(h_i, h_j) = \exp(-d_\theta(h_i, h_j)), \quad f_\theta \in [0, 1]. \quad (1)$$

The network is trained on labeled hash pairs $\{(h_i, h_j, y_{ij})\}$, where $y_{ij} = 1$ for perceptually similar images and $y_{ij} = 0$ for dissimilar ones. Positive pairs are generated using common image transformations such as resizing, compression, color changes, and cropping. Training uses a contrastive loss:

$$L = y_{ij} d_\theta(h_i, h_j)^2 + (1 - y_{ij}) \max(0, m - d_\theta(h_i, h_j))^2, \quad (2)$$

with margin $m > 0$ enforcing separation between dissimilar pairs.

Once trained, SiPHaD ranks database images for copy detection by computing similarity scores $s_{qj} = f_\theta(h_q, h_j)$ and returning the top- k matches. Unlike fixed perceptual hash comparisons, the learned similarity function operates in an embedding space, improving robustness to cropping, scaling, and other transformations, and enabling correct retrieval even from partial views.

TABLE III: Dataset characteristics and evaluation setup. Original images and distractors for PIHD and mCOCO.

Dataset	Source	Original	Distractors
PIHD [10]	ImageNet subset	240	23,040
mCOCO	MS COCO 2017 val	200	4,800

Fig. 3: Examples from PIHD (top row) and mCOCO (bottom row). The query is a modified image, with the left column displaying images similar or relevant to the original, and the right column showing dissimilar or irrelevant distractors.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

This section first introduces the datasets used in our experiments (Section IV-A). Then, it describes the system configuration and experimental procedures (Section IV-B).

A. Datasets

We evaluate perceptual hashing methods using two datasets: PIHD² and mCOCO³, covering both real-world and synthetic image modifications; see Table III.

PIHD [10] This dataset consists of selected ImageNet images enriched with additional web content. Each image has 8 different modifications and includes visually similar distractor images. For evaluation, the query set contains 30 images per modification, totaling 240 images (30×8), while the retrieval set comprises the corresponding original images along with 23,040 distractor images.

mCOCO Built from 5,000 images from the 2017 COCO validation set [37], this dataset was synthetically modified to emulate real-world transformations. Twelve perceptually modified variant categories were created. Table IV has 8 unimodified and 4 multimodified categories (each applying two transformations in random order per image). Overall, 244,200 images are generated by applying 1,221 transformations to 200 original images. To ensure a fair evaluation and a balanced distribution across modification categories, only 200 images per category are retained, yielding a final dataset of 2,400 images (200×12). The retrieval set consists of the original images as ground truth, supplemented with 4,800 distractor images.

Figure 3 shows an example of original images from PIHD (top row) and mCOCO (bottom row), along with similar images (green boxes) and dissimilar images (red boxes).

²<https://doi.org/10.57760/sciencedb.j00240.00016>

³<https://github.com/jmstf94/Perceptual-Hashing-Image-Retrieval.git>

TABLE IV: Image modification categories of mCOCO: 8 single and 4 double (combinations of two single categories).

Unimodified		
Transform	#Transf.	Details
Blur (Bl)	20	2D kernel blur ($x, y = 5-34$)
Text (Tx)	60	Random position, color, font size (20–30)
Resized (Re)	200	Random scaling (50–90%)
Cropped (Cr)	100	Random crop (5–25% per side)
Hue Shift (HS)	40	Hue shift (50–230)
Pixel Destroy (PD)	200	Rectangular noise region (15–35%)
Rotation (Rt)	40	Small rotation (5–15°)
Mirror (Mr)	1	Horizontal flip
Multimodified		
Transform	#Transf.	Details
Co1	140	HS + PD
Co2	160	Cr + Re
Co3	120	Tx + Bl
Co4	40	Rt + Mr

B. System Configuration

All experiments for PIHD and mCOCO were run on an Intel Core i5-12600K CPU (3.7GHz). Average query time were calculated to measure computational efficiency. SiPHaD was trained on a single NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3060 Ti GPU. Training was fast since the model takes hash codes as input, with the main bottleneck being data preparation and organization. Half of the training data used 256-bit average hashes, and half used cropped images from the original MS COCO retrieval set, ensuring no overlap with mCOCO queries.

We focus on average Recall@1 rather than Precision or F-score, as it reflects the ability to retrieve the most relevant top-ranked matches, which is critical for image copy detection. We evaluate average, difference, perceptual, and wavelet hashes at 64, 256, and 1024 bits using Hamming, Cosine, Jaccard, Weighted Chamfer, Convolution, Hatched, and N-Gram distances. Preliminary results show that Wavelet hash offers the best efficiency–robustness trade-off, so we focus on it in the results. For Weighted Chamfer, multiple k_2 values were tested, with 0.8 performing best.

V. RESULTS

This section presents hash-based retrieval results on PIHD (Section V-A) and mCOCO (Section V-B) across different hash types and distance metrics, focusing primarily on Wavelet hash (W-Hash). As discussed in Section IV, W-Hash is the most consistent across transformations and hash lengths, while other methods follow similar trends. We conclude with a summary (Section V-C).

A. Hash-based Retrieval Results on PIHD

In this section, we report average query times versus code length across different hashes and provide results for all unimodified images on PIHD, which contains only single modifications.

Figure 4 summarizes the efficiency of the evaluated hash representations on the PIHD dataset. It reports the average

TABLE V: Average Recall@1 on PIHD with Wavelet 256. The score is the average across modifications; bold marks the best, and underlining indicates the top-3 distances from different categories.

Category	Distances	Unmodified								Score
		Bl	Tx	Re	Cr	HS	PD	Rt	Mr	
Bitwise	Hamming	0.995	0.980	0.990	0.440	0.940	0.975	0.965	0.970	<u>0.907</u>
	Cosine	0.993	0.975	0.985	0.435	0.940	0.970	0.960	0.965	<u>0.903</u>
	Jaccard	0.993	0.975	0.985	0.435	0.940	0.970	0.960	0.965	0.903
Spatial-aware	Weighted Chamfer	0.995	0.985	0.992	0.480	0.950	0.975	0.970	0.975	<u>0.915</u>
	Convolution	0.995	0.985	0.992	0.480	0.950	0.975	0.970	0.975	<u>0.915</u>
	Hatched	0.988	0.985	0.991	0.462	0.940	0.975	0.975	0.975	0.911
Sequential	N-Gram	0.978	0.985	0.956	0.450	0.930	0.975	0.975	0.975	0.903
Neural	SiPHaD	0.995	0.985	0.992	0.505	0.950	0.975	0.980	0.975	<u>0.920</u>

Fig. 4: Average query time of Wavelet hash on PIHD dataset.

query time (in seconds) for each hash type across different code lengths, with the y-axis indicating the hash length and colors denoting the distance metrics; legend entries are sorted according to the 64-bit results. Overall, query time increases with hash length. Across all hash types, Recall@1 is largely consistent across different code lengths (64–1024 bits), indicating that increasing hash length has little effect on retrieval accuracy. Therefore, results are reported only for 256-bit hash codes.

Table V reports Recall@1 for the 256-bit Wavelet hash as a representative case. Other hash types follow similar trends and do not alter the overall conclusions. Each row corresponds to a distance metric, grouped by category as defined in Section III-B. Columns correspond to different unmodified transformations (Bl, Tx, Re, Cr, HS, PD, Rt, and Mr) as described in Section IV-A, and the final column reports the average Recall@1 across all transformations.

Across all settings, SiPHaD achieves the highest Recall@1 and best overall performance, demonstrating strong robustness across hash representations and content types. Among hash types, wavelet and difference hashes are more robust under challenging transformations such as cropping (Cr) and rotation

(Rt), while perceptual hashes perform competitively under moderate modifications. Average and difference hashes remain effective for simpler transformations such as blur (Bl), texture changes (Tx), and resizing (Re).

Regarding distance metrics, structure-aware approaches—Weighted Chamfer, Convolution, Hatched, and N-Gram—consistently outperform element-wise metrics such as Hamming, Cosine, and Jaccard, particularly under spatial transformations (e.g., Cr and Rt). This confirms that incorporating spatial structure into similarity computation improves robustness to geometric distortions. Overall, SiPHaD provides the best trade-off between accuracy and robustness across challenging transformations.

B. Hash-based Retrieval Results on mCOCO

This section focuses on mCOCO, showing the best-performing distance metrics for both unmodified and multi-modified images. We also include results analyzing the effect of crop percentage on average Recall@1, which this dataset allows.

We evaluate hash-based retrieval performance on the mCOCO dataset in this subsection. Based on the results of the previous section, we consider only 256-bit hashes. This choice offers superior performance while maintaining a favorable trade-off between hash length and computational cost. In addition, we compare only three distance measures: Hamming, Weighted Chamfer with a weight of 0.8, and the proposed SiPHaD, since the first two represent the best-performing and most commonly used distances, making them appropriate baselines.

Table VI presents the average Recall@1 on mCOCO using 256-bit wavelet hashes with 5-fold cross-validation [38]. Results for other perceptual hashes were also evaluated but are omitted since they show similar trends. The table is organized by distance measures, with columns covering unmodified transformations and multimodified images (Table IV). The final column reports the overall average across all cases for direct comparison. Overall, SiPHaD achieves the highest Recall@1 across both unmodified and multimodified images, showing strong robustness to transformations. Cropping remains the most challenging case, and multimodified images generally reduce performance for fixed distance metrics.

TABLE VI: Average Recall@1 on mCOCO across unmodified and multimodified variants, using Wavelet 256 hashes and distances.

Distances	Unimodified								Multimodified				Score
	Bl	Tx	Re	Cr	HS	PD	Rt	Mr	Co1	Co2	Co3	Co4	
Hamming	1.000	0.990	1.000	0.475	0.990	0.980	0.990	0.980	0.980	0.425	0.995	0.995	0.900
Weighted Chamfer	1.000	0.985	1.000	0.500	0.990	0.980	0.990	0.980	0.955	0.460	0.995	0.995	0.902
SiPHaD	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.555	1.000	0.980	1.000	1.000	0.980	0.525	0.995	0.995	0.919

Fig. 5: Effect of crop percentage using Wavelet 256 hash on average Recall@1 for different distance metrics on mCOCO dataset.

Figure 5 shows the effect of increasing crop percentage on mCOCO using the 256-bit Wavelet hash, measured by Average Recall@1. Three distance metrics are compared: Hamming, Weighted Chamfer, and SiPHaD. The x -axis indicates the cropped area as a percentage of the original image (0% to 26%), while the y -axis shows the average Recall@1 (0.0 to 1.0). Each distance is shown in a different color: Hamming (brown), Weighted Chamfer (orange), and SiPHaD (black), with SiPHaD highlighted using a dashed line and slightly thicker linewidth. As cropping increases, recall decreases. SiPHaD consistently performs the best and remains more stable even at higher crop levels. Weighted Chamfer usually outperforms Hamming, but its performance drops faster for some hashes. Overall, SiPHaD is the most robust distance metric when images are heavily cropped.

C. Summary

Results from PIHD (Section V-A) and mCOCO (Section V-B) show that standard distance measures often fail

to capture the true relationships between hashes. They may not always bring similar images closer or push different ones apart. In contrast, SiPHaD’s Siamese network learns these relationships from paired data, giving more accurate and robust similarity estimates across datasets and modifications. This robustness is especially visible under cropping. As the crop percentage increases, SiPHaD maintains higher retrieval performance than Hamming or Weighted Chamfer, while the other distances drop more sharply, showing that SiPHaD can better handle missing or occluded content. These results show that learning similarity in the hash space is more reliable than fixed distances, improving performance between hash types, datasets, and simple and complex modifications.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This work studies image copy detection under realistic modifications using perceptual hashing. We evaluated classical perceptual hashes with various similarity measures on PIHD and the new mCOCO dataset. Spatially-aware metrics, such as Weighted Chamfer, outperform simple bitwise distances by better capturing hash structure. To overcome the limitations of fixed distance measures, we proposed SiPHaD, a Siamese framework that learns similarity directly in the hash space. SiPHaD preserves the efficiency and security of perceptual hashing while significantly improving retrieval performance, particularly under challenging transformations such as cropping, rotation, and combined modifications. Across both datasets and multiple hash types, SiPHaD consistently achieves higher Recall@1 than classical metrics, demonstrating robust performance in both unimodified and multimodified scenarios. Future work will test more crop levels (%) and expand with more data the mCOCO.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work is supported by the Horizon Europe program under the grant agreement 101181380 AQUAMON, and by the EDIH-IS 2.0 project, grant number 101256863, DIGITAL-2025-EDIH-EU-EEA-08.

REFERENCES

- [1] H. Dos Santos, T. D. S. Martins, J. A. D. Barreto, L. H. V. Nakamura, C. M. Ranieri, R. E. De Grande, G. P. Rocha Filho, and R. I. Meneguette, "Chasam: An architecture based on perceptual hashing for image detection in computer forensics," *IEEE Access*, vol. 12, pp. 104 611–104 628, 2024.
- [2] D. García-Retuerta, Á. Bartolomé, P. Chamoso, and J. M. Corchado, "Counter-terrorism video analysis using hash-based algorithms," *Algorithms*, vol. 12, no. 5, p. 110, 2019.
- [3] J. De Geest, P. De Smet, L. Bonetto, P. Lambert, G. Van Wallendael, and H. Mareen, "Exploring human perception-aligned perceptual hashing," *IEEE Consumer Electronics Magazine*, 2025.
- [4] Y. Wan, Q. Yuan, S. Ji, L. He, and Y. Wang, "A survey of the image copy detection," in *2008 IEEE Conference on Cybernetics and Intelligent Systems*. IEEE, 2008, pp. 738–743.
- [5] A. Wary and A. Neelima, "A review on robust video copy detection," *International Journal of Multimedia Information Retrieval*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 61–78, 2019.
- [6] G. Awad, P. Over, and W. Kraaij, "Content-based video copy detection benchmarking at trecvid," *ACM Transactions on Information Systems (TOIS)*, vol. 32, no. 3, pp. 1–40, 2014.
- [7] W. Wang, Y. Sun, and Y. Yang, "A benchmark and asymmetrical-similarity learning for practical image copy detection," in *Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence*, vol. 37, no. 3, 2023, pp. 2672–2679.
- [8] Y. Zhou, X. Li, C. Xiong, H. Yao, and C. Qin, "A survey of perceptual hashing for multimedia," *ACM Transactions on Multimedia Computing, Communications and Applications*, 2025.
- [9] A. Hadmi, A. Rouijel *et al.*, "A novel approach for robust perceptual image hashing," *Computer and Information Science*, vol. 14, no. 3, pp. 1–38, 2021.
- [10] Z. Yuanding, F. Yaodong, and Q. Chuan, "Large-scale Image Dataset for Perceptual Hashing," Mar. 2025.
- [11] H. Lejsek, F. H. Asmundsson, B. T. Jónsson, and L. Amsaleg, "Scalability of local image descriptors: A comparative study," in *Proceedings of the 14th ACM International Conference on Multimedia*, 2006, pp. 589–598.
- [12] P. Suma, G. Kordopatis-Zilos, A. Iscen, and G. Toliás, "Ames: Asymmetric and memory-efficient similarity estimation for instance-level retrieval," in *European Conference on Computer Vision*. Springer, 2024, pp. 307–325.
- [13] L. Amsaleg, B. Þ. Jónsson, and H. Lejsek, "Scalability of the nv-tree: Three experiments," in *International Conference on Similarity Search and Applications*. Springer, 2018, pp. 59–72.
- [14] W. Tan, H. Guo, and R. Liu, "A fast partial video copy detection using knn and global feature database," in *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Winter Conference on Applications of Computer Vision*, 2022, pp. 2191–2199.
- [15] M. A. Elaskily, H. A. Elnemr, A. Sedik, M. M. Dessouky, G. M. El Banby, O. A. Elshakankiry, A. A. Khalaf, H. K. Aslan, O. S. Faragallah, and F. E. Abd El-Samie, "A novel deep learning framework for copy-moveforgery detection in images," *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, vol. 79, no. 27, pp. 19 167–19 192, 2020.
- [16] H. Liu, R. Wang, S. Shan, and X. Chen, "Deep supervised hashing for fast image retrieval," in *Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, 2016, pp. 2064–2072.
- [17] Z. Cao, M. Long, J. Wang, and P. S. Yu, "Hashnet: Deep learning to hash by continuation," in *Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Computer Vision*, 2017, pp. 5608–5617.
- [18] H. Zhu, M. Long, J. Wang, and Y. Cao, "Deep hashing network for efficient similarity retrieval," in *Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence*, vol. 30, no. 1, 2016.
- [19] Y. Hao, T. Mu, J. Y. Goulermas, J. Jiang, R. Hong, and M. Wang, "Unsupervised t-distributed video hashing and its deep hashing extension," *IEEE Transactions on Image Processing*, vol. 26, no. 11, pp. 5531–5544, 2017.
- [20] T. Hoang, T.-T. Do, T. V. Nguyen, and N.-M. Cheung, "Unsupervised deep cross-modality spectral hashing," *IEEE Transactions on Image Processing*, vol. 29, pp. 8391–8406, 2020.
- [21] H. K. Sarohi and F. U. Khan, "Image retrieval using perceptual hashing," *IOSR Journal of Computer Engineering (IOSR-JCE) e-ISSN*, pp. 2278–0661, 2013.
- [22] H. Farid, "An overview of perceptual hashing," *Journal of Online Trust and Safety*, vol. 1, no. 1, 2021.
- [23] H. Chen, H. Zhou, J. Zhang, D. Chen, W. Zhang, K. Chen, G. Hua, and N. Yu, "Perceptual hashing of deep convolutional neural networks for model copy detection," *ACM Transactions on Multimedia Computing, Communications and Applications*, vol. 19, no. 3, pp. 1–20, 2023.
- [24] Z. Huang, Z. Tang, X. Zhang, L. Ruan, and X. Zhang, "Perceptual image hashing with locality preserving projection for copy detection," *IEEE Transactions on Dependable and Secure Computing*, vol. 20, no. 1, pp. 463–477, 2021.
- [25] P. Samanta and S. Jain, "Analysis of perceptual hashing algorithms in image manipulation detection," *Procedia Computer Science*, vol. 185, pp. 203–212, 2021.
- [26] X. Sun and J. Zhou, "Deep perceptual hash based on hash center for image copyright protection," *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 120 551–120 562, 2022.
- [27] P. Subudhi and K. Kumari, "A fast and efficient large-scale near duplicate image retrieval system using double perceptual hashing," *Signal, Image and Video Processing*, vol. 18, no. 12, pp. 8565–8575, 2024.
- [28] V. Monga and B. L. Evans, "Perceptual image hashing via feature points: Performance evaluation and trade-offs," *IEEE Transactions on Image Processing*, vol. 15, no. 11,

- pp. 3452–3465, 2006.
- [29] X. Lv and Z. J. Wang, “Perceptual image hashing based on shape contexts and local feature points,” *IEEE Transactions on Information Forensics and Security*, vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 1081–1093, 2012.
- [30] A. Alzu’bi, A. Amira, and N. Ramzan, “Semantic content-based image retrieval: A comprehensive study,” *Journal of Visual Communication and Image Representation*, vol. 32, pp. 20–54, 2015.
- [31] S. Liu and Z. Huang, “Efficient image hashing with geometric invariant vector distance for copy detection,” *ACM Transactions on Multimedia Computing, Communications, and Applications (TOMM)*, vol. 15, no. 4, pp. 1–22, 2019.
- [32] Y. Li and W. Zhang, “Robust image fingerprinting algorithm based on local and global content dependencies,” *IEEE Signal Processing Letters*, vol. 31, pp. 336–340, 2024.
- [33] T.-Y. Lin, M. Maire, S. Belongie, J. Hays, P. Perona, D. Ramanan, P. Dollár, and C. L. Zitnick, “Microsoft coco: Common objects in context,” in *European Conference on Computer Vision*. Springer, 2014, pp. 740–755.
- [34] J. Deng, W. Dong, R. Socher, L.-J. Li, K. Li, and L. Fei-Fei, “Imagenet: A large-scale hierarchical image database,” in *2009 IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*. IEEE, 2009, pp. 248–255.
- [35] J. Dong, W. Wang, and T. Tan, “Casia image tampering detection evaluation database,” in *2013 IEEE China Summit and International Conference on Signal and Information Processing*. IEEE, 2013, pp. 422–426.
- [36] C. E. Duchon, “Lanczos filtering in one and two dimensions,” *Journal of Applied Meteorology (1962-1982)*, pp. 1016–1022, 1979.
- [37] T. Lin, M. Maire, S. J. Belongie, L. D. Bourdev, R. B. Girshick, J. Hays, P. Perona, D. Ramanan, P. Dollár, and C. L. Zitnick, “Microsoft COCO: common objects in context,” *CoRR*, vol. abs/1405.0312, 2014. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1405.0312>
- [38] T.-T. Wong and P.-Y. Yeh, “Reliable accuracy estimates from k-fold cross validation,” *IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering*, vol. 32, no. 8, pp. 1586–1594, 2019.